

Graded Hydrolysis of Cashew Nut Shell Polysaccharide. Isolation of the Neutral Oligosaccharides and Characterisation of Disaccharide

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Water soluble polysaccharide occurring in cashewnut shell furnishes on mild hydrolysis one disaccharide, one trisaccharide and two tetrasaccharides, all of them being neutral in character. Disaccharide has been identified as 3-O- β -D-Galactopyranosyl-D-Galactose from its physical properties, hydrolytic pattern and periodate oxidation reaction.

It has been shown earlier¹ that the water soluble polysaccharide occurring in cashew nut (*Anacardium occidentale*) shell is composed of L-rhamnose, L-arabinose, D-galactose and D-galacturonic acid, the three neutral sugars being present in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 17. The polysaccharide when subjected to partial acid hydrolysis gives rise to a mixture of acidic and neutral oligosaccharides. The present communication, deals with the isolation of three neutral oligosaccharides and characterisation of the disaccharide.

Water soluble cashew nut shell polysaccharide upon hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid (0.1 N) for 6 hr furnished a mixture of acidic and neutral oligosaccharides along with neutral sugars consisting of L-rhamnose, L-arabinose and D-galactose. Preliminary paper chromatographic examination of the neutral oligosaccharides (fraction A) reveals the presence of four components. Besides, there were two faint spots in the paper chromatogram corresponding to two more oligosaccharides but they could not be isolated in subsequent steps. It may also be mentioned that identical spots of neutral oligosaccharides were obtained when the polysaccharide was hydrolysed at room temperature following the procedure of Parikh and Jones². Resolution of (A) into its different components was first attempted on an charcoal-celite column³ using water containing increasing amount of ethanol as eluant. A large number of fractions were collected but each of them was found to carry more than one component on paper chromatographic analysis. Appropriate fractions were then combined and concentrated to a syrup which was finally resolved into its components by chromatography on a number of Whatman no 3 MM filter paper sheets. Thus one disaccharide and three oligosaccharides could be isolated in an homogeneous state. A determination of degree of polymerisation of the oligosaccharides (Table II, Experimental) indicated that one of the three was a trisaccharide, the remaining two being tetrasaccharides.

Disaccharide (I), $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +59.6^\circ$, m.p., 169–71°, on complete acid hydrolysis furnishes D-galactose only. The linkage between two galactose moieties has been ascertained from the periodate oxidation reaction. Methyl glycoside derivative of (I) upon oxidation with periodate produced one mole of formic acid with concomitant absorption of two moles of

1. S. Bose and P. A. A. Menon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 1092.
2. V. M. Parikh and J. K. N. Jones, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 327.
3. R. L. Whistler and D. F. Durso, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 677.

periodate. Further the periodate oxidised products on acid hydrolysis give rise to galactose only. All these observations indicate the presence of 1 → 3 linkage between the two galactose moieties. Hence (I) may be designated as 3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl-D-galactose. The $[\alpha]_D$, m.p. and R_{gal} values of (I) also agree with the reported values of the compound⁴. Further work is in progress for the characterisation of the remaining trisaccharide and tetrasaccharides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were done under reduced pressure at 45–50°. Specific rotations are equilibrium values and melting points are uncorrected. Paper chromatography analyses were carried out by descending method of Whatman No. 1 or 3 MM filter paper sheets with the following solvent systems (V/V) : (S₁) Butanol-Ethanol-Water (4 : 1 : 5, upper layer), (S₂) Pyridine-Ethyl-Acetate-Water-Acetic acid (5 : 5 : 3 : 1); (S₃) Ethyl Acetate-Acetic Acid-Butanol-Water (4 : 3 : 2 : 2); (S₄) Ethyl Acetate-Pyridine-Water (10 : 4 : 3) and (S₅) Ethyl Acetate-pyridine-Water (5 : 2 : 7). Spray reagents used are (R₁) Alkaline Silver Nitrate and (R₂) *p*-Anisidine phosphate.

Partial hydrolysis of water soluble polysaccharide : The water soluble polysaccharide (15 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 6 hr with sulphuric acid (0.1 *N*, 150 ml.). The hydrolysate was cooled, neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to syrup. To obtain the neutral sugars (fraction A), the syrup was exhaustively extracted with boiling methanol (150 ml.) for 6 hr and methanolic extract was again concentrated to syrup. The amorphous residue (fraction B) consisting of the barium salts of acidic sugars was washed thoroughly with methanol and kept aside for further investigation. Paper chromatography of the syrup (A), using solvent S₃ and spray reagents R₁, showed four distinct spots for oligosaccharides having $R_{cellobiose}$ values 0.98, 0.81, 0.30 and 0.22 respectively, besides the spots corresponding to rhamnose, arabinose and galactose. Two more faint spots ($R_{cellobiose}$ 0.55 and 0.45) corresponding to oligosaccharides were also discernible in the papergram. Identical spots for neutral oligosaccharides appeared when the polysaccharide was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (6 *N*) for 23 days at room temperature².

Resolution of (A) into its component sugars was carried out by adsorbing the syrup (5 g.) on a column (49 × 2.5 cm) of charcoal-celite (1 : 1 w/w). The column was first eluted with water (1 : 1) to remove the monosaccharides, rhamnose, arabinose and galactose. Subsequently, the column was washed with water containing increasing proportions of ethanol and different fractions (100 ml. each) obtained were examined paper chromatographically (solvent S₃, spray reagent R₁). The results are tabulated below :

TABLE I

Column chromatographic separation of Fraction (A)

Fraction Nos.	Eluant	Volume of Eluant in litres	* Oligosaccharide $R_{cellobiose}$
1-20	0.5% Ethanol	2	0.98, 0.81
21-50	5% "	3	0.81, 0.30
51-66	15% "	1.6	0.81, 0.30, 0.22

4. G. O. Aspinnall and T. B. Christensen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3461.

The mixture of oligosaccharides was finally resolved into its components by chromatography on Whatman No. 3 MM filter paper sheets (solvent S₃). The strips corresponding to individual compounds were eluted with water, and the elutes were concentrated, separately to obtain the following oligosaccharides in a homogeneous state. The yield, m.p.s, specific rotations and D.P. values of the compounds are given below (Table II). Degree of polymerisation was determined according to the method of Peat, Whelan and Roberts⁵.

TABLE II

Neutral oligosaccharides from the water soluble polysaccharide

Oligosaccharide	Yield (in g.)	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$	R _{cellobiose}	D.P.
I	0.1024	169-70°	+59.6	0.98(R _{gal} 0.4)	2
II	0.2246	139-41°	+31.8	0.81	3
III	0.1484	120-22°	+6.5	0.31	4
IV	0.3026	128-30°	—	0.22	4

Hydrolysis of the Disaccharide : Disaccharide (0.02 g. R_{gal} 0.4 in solvent S₄) was heated on a steam bath for 10 hr. with sulphuric acid (N, 5 ml.). The hydrolysate was cooled, neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to syrup. Paper chromatography of the syrup (solvent S₁ and spray reagent R₁) showed spot corresponding to D-galactose only.

Periodate oxidation of the methylglycoside derivative of disaccharide and hydrolysis of the periodate oxidised product : Disaccharide (0.08 g.) was converted into its methylglycoside derivative by refluxing with methanolic hydrogen chloride (4%, 25 ml.) for 4 hr. An aqueous solution of the compound (0.0502 g.) in 20 ml. was treated with sodium metaperiodate solution (0.4836 g. in 25 ml.) and kept as such in dark for 7 days at room temperature. The volume of the solution was then made upto 100 ml. and aliquots (5 ml. each) were removed for the estimation of the periodate consumed⁶ and formic acid liberated^{7,8} as a result of oxidation. Formic acid produced and periodate consumed (mean value) at the final stage was found to be 0.91 and 2.19 moles respectively per mole of the methylglycoside derivative of the disaccharide.

In another experiment, excess of periodate was removed from an aliquot (25 ml.) by treatment with ethylene glycol. The resulting solution after being freed from inorganic

5. Stanley Peat, W. J. Whelan and J. G. Roberts, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2258.

6. J. C. Rankin and A. Jeans, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4435.

7. T. G. Halsall, E. L. Hirst and J. K. N. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1427.

8. M. Abdel-Akher and F. Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 994.

ions by treatment with freshly regenerated cation and anion exchange resins, was acidified with sulphuric acid to 1*N* and heated on a boiling water bath for 6 hr. The hydrolysate was neutralised, filtered and concentrated to a syrup. Paper chromatography of the syrup (solvent S_5 , spray reagent R_1) furnished a distinct spot for galactose only.

The authors express their thanks to Shri S. C. Gupta, Director and Dr. S. Mukherjee, Professor of Sugar Chemistry for their interests. One of the authors (P.L.S.) acknowledges with thanks the grant of a scholarship by the Ministry of Education, Government of India.

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Received August 8, 1970